

MODERN APPROACHES AND INNOVATIONS IN CARDIOSURGERY AND
ANGIOSURGERY

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Relevance of the problem: The department of X-ray endovascular methods of diagnosis and treatment is an innovative and high-tech structure of the vascular center, which allows examination of all vascular areas of the body, reconstruction of the angioarchitecture of the studied organs in 3D format using unique software, and allows planning and implementation of optimal treatment based on data.

In the cardiology department, he closely cooperates with all treatment and diagnostic departments and performs a full range of diagnostic procedures and therapeutic endovascular interventions in accordance with advanced European protocols.

Aims and objectives of the study: The highest qualification of specialists, modern equipment and tools, optimal diagnosis and treatment, which are used as part of an individual approach to the patient.

Examination methods: Coronary angiography, ventriculography, heart shuntography
Angiography of brachiocephalic vessels, including. carotid, subclavian and vertebral arteries

Angiography of intracranial arteries

Angiopulmonography

Angiography of the visceral branches of the aorta, including. renal and mesenteric arteries, celiac trunk, etc.

Angiography of pelvic arteries: iliac arteries and their branches (including uterine arteries)

Angiography of the arteries of the lower extremities

Cavography and phlebography of the lower extremities

Determination of the vascular structure of various organs and formations

Therapeutic interventions:

cardiac surgeon

Endovascular removal of blood clots in acute myocardial infarction and ischemic stroke

Balloon angioplasty and stenting of coronary arteries

Including balloon angioplasty and brachiocephalic stenting. carotid, subclavian and vertebral arteries

Balloon angioplasty and stenting of renal arteries

Balloon angioplasty and stenting of the arteries of the pelvis, upper and lower extremities

Endovascular occlusion of cerebral aneurysms

Uterine artery embolization (standard and original methods)

Embolization of other blood vessels, including for bleeding, anastomosis, arteriovenous malformations and other pathologies

Embolization of cavernous hemangiomas and liver tumors

Restoring the patency of the fallopian tubes in case of infertility

Implantation and removal of the vena cava filter

Treatment of arrhythmias using radiofrequency ablation (RFA-ablation).

Placement and adjustment of various types of pacemakers

ADVANTAGES OF ENDOVASCULAR TECHNIQUES:

cardiac surgeon

Organ preservation operations to prevent amputation

Minimal risk of postoperative complications (less than 0.1%).

A possibility to treat patients for whom traditional surgical interventions are contraindicated or ineffective.

There are no postoperative scars. All interventions are performed through a single puncture of the skin of the upper or lower leg

cardiac surgeon

Short operation (up to 60 minutes)

It does not require the anesthesia used in traditional surgery

The ability to completely restore the body in the shortest possible time

Minimum length of hospital stay (approximately 1-3 days)

Immediate improvement of the patient's condition, rapid rehabilitation and elimination of unpleasant symptoms of the disease

Preservation and restoration of functional and reproductive ability of the patient

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